

Deliverable: 6.4

Title: Scientific and popular science publications – first batch

Project information

Project Title	Networking for excellence in the development of innovative, consumer-oriented horticultural food products using the Living Lab approach
Acronym:	HortiFoodTrends
Grant agreement:	101159293
Topic	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01 - Twinning Bottom-Up
Type of action	Horizon - Coordination and Support Action
Granting authority	European Research Executive Agency
Start date of the project	1 June 2024
Duration	36 months
Project Coordinator	Monika Mieszczakowska-Frąć
Project Website	www.hortifoodtrends.eu

Deliverable information

Deliverable title	Scientific and popular science publications – first batch
Deliverable number	6.4
Deliverable version	1.0
Work Package	WP6 - Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation
Contractual date of delivery	M17 - 31/10/2025
Actual date of delivery	M17 - 30/10/2025
Deliverable type:	R – Document, report
Responsible Partner	InHort

Authoring & Approval

Authors	Monika Mieszczakowska-Frąc
Reviewers	Michael Bom Frøst, Ronan Symoneaux,
Approved for submission	Dorota Konopacka, Monika Mieszczakowska-Frąc

Dissemination level

PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified S-UE/EU-S	UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

Document History

Version	Date	Description of Change
V0.1	25/10/2025	First draft
V0.2	27/10/2025	Second draft version incorporating 1 review comments
V0.3	29/10/2025	Final draft send to PC
V1.0	30/10/2025	Final version submitted to EC by the PC

Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101159293. Disclaimer: This report only reflects the views of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in [D6.4 Scientific and popular science publications – first batch](#)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. INTRODUCTION	5
2. ACHIEVEMENTS	6
2.1. List of scientific publications, abstracts	12
2.2. List of posters.....	14

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable 6.4 “Scientific and popular science publications – first batch” describes the elaborated approaches that contribute to producing high-quality project results as publications, oral presentations, and posters. The deliverable also presents the current state of scientific activity.

Deliverable D6.4 provides information on the strategy followed by the consortium in terms of disseminating the project’s results towards the consortium's strategy for disseminating the project’s results to the scientific community. The consortium maintains an evolving list of target conferences, workshops, and journals (including relevant special issues) hosted in D6.2 "Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan". This list is a “living document” that all partners update.

1. INTRODUCTION

The HortiFoodTrends project is contributing to scientific publications, posters, and presentations within the disciplines of science of agriculture and horticulture as well as nutrition and food technology, including the use of models, algorithms and other state-of-the-art techniques in the sensory evaluation of food products and consumer research.

During the first period of the project, particular emphasis was placed on enhancing InHort scientists' knowledge in sensory research through a series of workshops (WP1) and internships with partners (WP2). To intensify preparation for joint research publications, the Consortium developed a framework to incorporate the first prototypes of berry-based products developed in WP4 into the training program. This approach enabled the acquisition of scientific data for use in scientific publications or dissemination materials for the HortiFoodTrends project. Table 1 and Table 2 in this deliverable present the activities related to joint publication preparation and conference attendance.

With respect to open access to publications and FAIR research data management, HortiFoodTrends strictly adheres to the open science guidelines specified in the Horizon Europe Programme. HortiFoodTrends pursues the publication of project results in open-access venues when this option is optimal and possible for a particular publication in terms of scientific impact and visibility, as well as the availability of funds for publication fees. Irrespective, publications are also deposited in the trusted repository Zenodo. The peer-reviewed scientific publications are published under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY 4.0). The HortiFoodTrend project is implemented under the HORIZON-WIDERA (Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area) program, which focuses on strengthening the capacity and improving the scientific quality of countries with lower research potential.

Increasing the quantity and quality of scientific publications is therefore a key objective of the HortiFoodTrends project, which will enhance the visibility of InHort researchers within the international scientific community.

Articles published by the Fruit and Vegetables Storage and Processing Department (the department involved in the project) are presented in Table 3, counting from the inception of the HortiFoodTrends project. 27 peer-reviewed publications have been published, 26 of which have status open access. Additionally, 4 articles have been published in open access as non-peer-reviewed preprints.

The consortium expects to achieve the target of five joint publications in the second half of the project, based on ongoing work within WP4 and short-term staff exchanges. Currently, one joint manuscript is being prepared and is planned for submission in November/ December 2025.

2. ACHIEVEMENTS

Table 1. Publications in journals within the project provided by Joint Exploratory Research

	Authors		Title	Publication	Year	PID	Open-access URL	status
1.	Dawid Wieloch, Dorota Konopacka	InHort	Black Chokeberry Extracts (<i>Aronia melanocarpa</i>) as an Ingredient of Functional Food – Potential, Challenges and Directions of Development	Molecules/MDPI/ Preprints/open access not peer-reviewed	2025	Doi:10.20944/preprints202510.0178.v1 Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/17468494	open access	delivered
2.	Dawid Wieloch, Dorota Konopacka	InHort	Black Chokeberry Extracts (<i>Aronia melanocarpa</i>) as an Ingredient of Functional Food – Potential, Challenges and Directions of Development	Molecules/MDPI/ peer-reviewed open access	2025	https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules30214237	open access	delivered
3.	Jan Piecko, M. Mieszczakowska-Frać, N.Dickinson, A.Wrzodak, K.Celejewska, M.B.Frøst, B.Lange, C.Dandenell, J.Lewandowicz, P.Jankowska	InHort/UCPH	tentative title "Ultrasound Treatment in Berry Puree Production: Effects on Sensory, Rheological, and Chemical Properties")		2025/ 2026	Not available yet	Not available yet	Under preparation Submission planned in Nov/Dec 2025

Table 2. Conference Publications within the project provided by Joint Exploratory Research

	Authors		Title	Where	When	Comment
1.	Dorota Konopacka	InHORT	PODEJŚCIE LIVING LAB sposób na wykreowanie innowacyjnych produktów o znaczącym potencjale rynkowym i właściwościach funkcjonalnych (in polish)	FoodFakty Summit, Łódź, Poland	06-07.11.2024	Oral presentation
2.	Sebastian Siarkowski, Dorota Konopacka, Monika Mieszczakowska-Frać, Alexia Jauniau, Agnès Giboreau, Dawid Wieloch	InHort, LYFE	Living Lab as support for the processing of polish berry fruits	International Scientific Conference on Food Sensory Science: SEASONED in 4 Seasons Wrocław, Poland	25-26.06.2025	Poster (see chapter 2.2)
3.	Alexia Jauniau, Sebastian Siarkowski, Dawid Wieloch, Monika Mieszczakowska-Frać, Jan Piecko, Jan Zdulski, Marie Natalizio, Agnès Giboreau	InHort, LYFE	Innovation driven by consumer ideation and validated in real-meal situation: an application to polish berries unknown in France	16 th Pangborn Sensory Science Symposium - Connecting Senses & Minds!	17-21.08.2025	Poster (see chapter 2.2)
4.	Dorota Konopacka, Sebastian Siarkowski, Monika Mieszczakowska-Frać, Dawid Wieloch	InHort	Sensory living-lab as opportunity for "super" berry fruit product adoption	16 th Pangborn Sensory Science Symposium - Connecting Senses & Minds!	17-21.08.2025	Poster (see chapter 2.2)

Table 3. Publications published by InHort’s research departments engaged into project in open-access and in peer-reviewed journals. In relation to kye project impact (KPI 1 and KPI 16).

No.	Publications after June 2024 (Project HFT start) /active link/	Open Access	Peer-reviewed	citation
1	Figorilli, S. i in. (2025) „A preliminary model for determining a soil quality index including biological data implemented through a QR code application”, Smart Agricultural Technology, 12, s. 101106. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atech.2025.101106.	YES	YES	0
2	Gendaszewska, D. i in. (2025) „Utilization of Protein Hydrolysates from Animal Waste for the Production of Biostimulants in Wheat Cultivation (Triticum aestivum L.)”, Fibres & Textiles in Eastern Europe, 33(1), s. 40–48. https://doi.org/10.2478/ftee-2025-0004.	YES	YES	1
3	Grzegorzewska, M., Szczech, M., i in. (2024) „Addition of Fresh Herbs to Fresh-Cut Iceberg Lettuce: Impact on Quality and Storability”, Agriculture, 14(8), s. 1266. https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture14081266.	YES	YES	1
4	Grzegorzewska, M., Szwejda-Grzybowska, J., i in. (2024) „Postharvest LED Treatment of Tomatoes Harvested at an Early Stage of Coloration”, Agronomy-Basel, 14(11), s. 2727. https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy14112727.	YES	YES	3
5	Grzegorzewska, M. i Szwejda-Grzybowska, J. (2025) „The Impact of Controlled and Dynamically Controlled Atmospheres on the Storage Ability and Sustainable Supply Chain of Zucchini Fruit”, Sustainability, 17(19), s. 8781. https://doi.org/10.3390/su17198781.	YES	YES	0
6	Keller-Przybylkowicz, S. i in. (2025) „Interactions Between Seasonal Temperature Changes, Activities of Selected Genes and Fruit Quality in Malus domestica Borkh.”, Agronomy-Basel, 15(4), s. 908. https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy15040908.	YES	YES	0
7	Kowalska, B. i in. (2025) „The potential of volatiles from Brassica juncea seeds against grey mould agent Botrytis cinerea and their effect on storage and sensory quality of spinach leaves”, Plant Protection Science, 61(1), s. 66–76. https://doi.org/10.17221/44/2024-PPS.	YES	YES	1
8	Kowalska, B. i Wrzodak, A. (2025) „Application Potential of Lactic Acid Bacteria in Horticultural Production”, Sustainability, 17(4), s. 1385. https://doi.org/10.3390/su17041385.	YES	YES	1

9	Mieszczakowska-Frac, M., Dickinson, N.J. i Konopacka, D. (2025) „Effect of Postharvest Ripening on the Phytochemical Composition and Antioxidant Properties of Fruits from Ten Plum (<i>Prunus domestica</i> L.) Cultivars”, <i>Agronomy-Basel</i>, 15(6), s. 1351. https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy15061351.	YES	YES	1
10	Noutfia, Y. i in. (2024) „Non-Destructive Monitoring of External Quality of Date Palm Fruit (<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i> L.) During Frozen Storage Using Digital Camera and Flatbed Scanner”, <i>Sensors</i>, 24(23), s. 7560. https://doi.org/10.3390/s24237560.	YES	YES	3
11	Noutfia, Y., Ropelewska, E., Szwejda-Grzybowska, J., Mieszczakowska-Fr, M., i in. (2025) „Effects of mild infrared and convective drying on physicochemical properties, polyphenol compounds, and image features of two date palm cultivars: «Mejhoul» and «Boufeggous»”, <i>Lwt-Food Science and Technology</i>, 218, s. 117502. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2025.117502.	YES	YES	8
12	Noutfia, Y., Ropelewska, E., Szwejda-Grzybowska, J., Jozwiak, Z., Siarkowski, S., i in. (2025) „Evaluation of Storage Stability of Date Fruit (<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i> L.) at Two Levels of Relative Humidity Based on Selected Functional Compounds and Image Features”, <i>Foods</i>, 14(18), s. 3189. https://doi.org/10.3390/foods14183189.	YES	YES	0
13	Noutfia, Y., Ropelewska, E., Szwejda-Grzybowska, J., Jozwiak, Z., Mieszczakowska-Frac, M., i in. (2025) „Impact of Prolonged Frozen Storage on «Mejhoul» Date Palm Cultivar Based on Selected Qualitative Characteristics”, <i>Horticulturae</i>, 11(7), s. 731. https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae11070731.	YES	YES	1
14	Piecko, J. i in. (2024) „WPŁYW RODZAJU HOMOGENIZACJI NA WŁAŚCIWOŚCI REOLOGICZNE I ZAWARTOŚĆ ZWIĄZKÓW BIOAKTYWNYCH W MĘTNYM SOKU Z TRUSKAWEK”, <i>Zywnosc Nauka Technologia Jakosc/Food Science Technology Quality</i>, 31(3), s. 171–185. https://doi.org/10.15193/zntj/2024/140/517.	YES	YES	(not indexed)
15	Piecko, J. i in. (2025) „Effect of Ultrasound-Assisted Convective Drying on the Content of Bioactive Compounds and Drying Rate of Strawberry Slices”, <i>Applied Sciences-Basel</i>, 15(16), s. 8947. https://doi.org/10.3390/app15168947.	YES	YES	0
16	Ropelewska, E., Szwejda-Grzybowska, J., Wrzodak, A. i Mieszczakowska-Frac, M. (2024) „Determination of the Correlation Between Image Parameters and Chemical Properties of Red Sweet Bell Pepper During Fermentation”, <i>Acta Universitatis Cibiniensis. Series E: Food Technology</i>, 28(2), s. 145–158. https://doi.org/10.2478/aucft-2024-0012.	YES	YES	(not indexed)

17	Ropelewska, E., Szwejda-Grzybowska, J., Wrzodak, A. i Mieszczakowska-Frac, M. (2024) „Non-Destructive Monitoring of Sweet Pepper Samples After Selected Periods of Lacto-Fermentation”, Agriculture-Basel, 14(11), s. 1855. https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture14111855.	YES	YES	1
18	Ropelewska, E., Wrzodak, A., i in. (2025) „Application of Imaging Technology and Machine Learning to Assess the Behavior of Parthenocarpic and Non-Parthenocarpic Cucumber Cultivars Under Lacto-Fermentation”, Acta Universitatis Cibiniensis. Series E: Food Technology, 29(1), s. 89–98. https://doi.org/10.2478/aucft-2025-0007.	YES	YES	(not indexed)
19	Ropelewska, E., Dickinson, N.J., i in. (2025) „Relationships Between Chemical Properties, Color Parameters, and Image Features of New Clones of Apples (<i>Malus domestica</i> L.) from Ecological Cultivation”, Sustainability, 17(10), s. 4317. https://doi.org/10.3390/su17104317.	YES	YES	0
20	Ropelewska, E., Szwejda-Grzybowska, J., i in. (2025) „The Estimation of Phenolic Compounds, Sugars, and Acids of the Cultivar and Clones of Red-Fleshed Apples Based on Image Features”, Foods, 14(7), s. 1138. https://doi.org/10.3390/foods14071138.	YES	YES	2
21	Ropelewska, E., Konopacka, D. i Piecko, J. (2025) „Comparison of the Sensory Quality, Image Textures and Color Parameters of Black Chokeberries Dried in a Frozen State by Simultaneous Osmo-Microwave-Vacuum Drying Using Different Osmotic Solutions”, Acta Universitatis Cibiniensis. Series E: Food Technology, 29(1), s. 43–54. https://doi.org/10.2478/aucft-2025-0003.	YES	YES	(not indexed)
22	Ropelewska, E., Szwejda-Grzybowska, J. i Mieszczakowska-Fr, M. (2025) „The application of image textures and physicochemical parameters for quality monitoring of freeze-dried cubes and slices of red-fleshed apples”, Journal of Food Composition and Analysis, 145, s. 107763. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2025.107763.	NO	YES	0
23	Wrzodak, A. i in. (2025) „Red Pepper Fermentation with Geothermal Mineral Water: Impact on Nutritional Profile and Quality Characteristics”, Agronomy, 15(10), s. 2279. https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy15102279.	YES	YES	0
24	Zdulski, J.A., Rutkowski, K.P. i Konopacka, D. (2024) „Strategies to Extend the Shelf Life of Fresh and Minimally Processed Fruit and Vegetables with Edible Coatings and Modified Atmosphere Packaging”, Applied Sciences-Basel, 14(23), s. 11074. https://doi.org/10.3390/app142311074.	YES	YES	8
25	Sikorska-Zimny Kalina i in. (2025). The Effect of Different Ethanol Concentrations on Functional Properties in Apple Macerates. Journal of Nutrition and Food Security, 10(3), 423-432. https://publish.kne-publishing.com/index.php/JNFS/article/view/19241/18070	YES	YES	

26	Beneduce, L.; Piergiacomo, F.; Sikorska-Zimny, K. (2024) Different Nutritional Regimes in a Tomato Soilless System Affect the Bacterial Communities with Consequences on the Crop Quality. Agriculture 2024, 14, 2254. https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture14122254	YES	YES	
27	Wieloch, D.; Konopacka, D. Black Chokeberry Extracts (Aronia melanocarpa) as an Ingredient of Functional Food—Potential, Challenges and Directions of Development. Molecules 2025, 30, 4237. https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules30214237	YES	YES	
	Preprints			
25	Grzegorzewska, M. i Szwejda-Grzybowska, J. (2025) „Quality of Zucchini Stored in Controlled and Dynamically Controlled Atmospheres”. Biology and Life Sciences. Dostępne na: https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202508.1700.v1.		NO	
26	Keller-Przybyłkiewicz, S. i in. (2025) „The Impact of Seasonal Temperature Fluctuations on Genotype x Phenotype Interactions in Malus domestica Borkh.” Biology and Life Sciences. Dostępne na: https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202503.0560.v1.		NO	
27	Skorupińska, A. i in. (2025) „The Influence of Storage Technologies on the Quality and Storability of Blackcurrant (Ribes nigrum) Tihope cv.” Biology and Life Sciences. Dostępne na: https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202510.0720.v1.		NO	
28	Wieloch, D. i Konopacka, D. (2025) „Black Chokeberry Extracts (Aronia melanocarpa) as an Ingredient of Functional Food – Potential, Challenges and Directions of Development”. Biology and Life Sciences. Dostępne na: https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202510.0178.v1.		NO	

2.1. List of scientific publications, abstracts

[Doi:10.20944/preprints202510.0178.v1](https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202510.0178.v1)

Preprints.org is a free multidisciplinary platform providing preprint service that is dedicated to making early versions of research outputs permanently available and citable. Preprints posted at Preprints.org appear in Web of Science, Crossref, Google Scholar, Scilit, Europe PMC.

Copyright: This open access article is published under a Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license, which permit the free download, distribution, and reuse, provided that the author and preprint are cited in any reuse.

Preprints.org (www.preprints.org) | NOT PEER-REVIEWED | Posted: 2 October 2025 | [doi:10.20944/preprints202510.0178.v1](https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202510.0178.v1)

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions, and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions, or products referred to in the content.

Review

Black Chokeberry Extracts (*Aronia melanocarpa*) as an Ingredient of Functional Food – Potential, Challenges and Directions of Development

Dawid Wieloch * and Dorota Konopacka

The National Institute of Horticultural Research, Fruit and Vegetable Storage and Processing Department, HortiFood Processing Centre, Rybickiego 15/17, 96-100 Skierniewice, Poland

* Correspondence: dawid.wieloch@inhort.pl

Abstract

Functional foods are gaining global importance as consumer demand for products delivering health benefits beyond basic nutrition increases. Black chokeberry (*Aronia melanocarpa*) is a promising candidate in this field, due to its exceptionally high content of bioactive compounds, particularly polyphenols with well-documented health-promoting properties. This article reviews the current state of knowledge on the definition of functional foods and the health benefits of chokeberries, with special emphasis given to their extracts as promising ingredients for novel product development. Efficient recovery methods for bioactive compounds from fruits, pomace, and leaves are discussed, including advances in green extraction technologies such as ultrasound- and microwave-assisted extraction, supercritical fluids, and enzyme-assisted methods. Stabilization approaches, including microencapsulation and freeze-drying, which enhance the stability and bioavailability of phenolics, are also highlighted. The impact of aronia extracts on technological and sensory parameters of food is analyzed. Applications in beverages, baked goods, dairy, and meat products demonstrate improved antioxidant capacity and storability; however, astringency remains a major sensory challenge. Future perspectives include optimizing processing strategies and developing synergistic formulations to maximize health benefits while ensuring consumer acceptance.

Keywords: extracts; chokeberry; functional food; polyphenols; anthocyanins

Open Access Review

Black Chokeberry Extracts (*Aronia melanocarpa*) as an Ingredient of Functional Food—Potential, Challenges and Directions of Development

by Dawid Wieloch*

HortiFood Processing Centre, Fruit and Vegetable Storage and Processing Department, The National Institute of Horticultural Research, Rybickiego 15/17, 96-100 Skierniewice, Poland

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

Molecules **2025**, *30*(21), 4237; <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules30214237> (registering DOI)

Submission received: 30 September 2025 / Revised: 28 October 2025 / Accepted: 29 October 2025 /

Published: 30 October 2025

(This article belongs to the Special Issue Extraction and Analysis of New Bioactive Compounds Derived from Natural Products, 2nd Edition)

Download

Browse Figures

Versions Notes

Abstract

Functional food is gaining global importance as consumer demand for products delivering health benefits beyond basic nutrition increases. Black chokeberry (*Aronia melanocarpa*) is a promising candidate in this field, due to its exceptionally high content of bioactive compounds, particularly polyphenols with well-documented health-promoting properties. This article reviews the current state of knowledge about the functional food definition and the health benefits of chokeberries, with special emphasis given to their extracts as promising ingredients for novel product development. Efficient recovery methods for bioactive compounds from fruits, pomace, and leaves were discussed, including advances in green extraction technologies such as ultrasound- and microwave-assisted extraction, supercritical fluid extraction and enzyme-assisted extraction. Stabilization approaches, including microencapsulation and freeze-drying, which enhance the stability and bioavailability of phenolics, were also highlighted. The impact of aronia extracts on technological and sensory parameters of food was investigated. Applications in beverages, baked goods, dairy, and meat products demonstrate improved antioxidant capacity and storability. However, astringency remains a major sensory challenge. Future perspectives include optimization of processing strategies and developing synergistic formulations to maximize health benefits while ensuring consumer acceptance.

Keywords: green extracts; chokeberry; functional food; polyphenols; anthocyanins

2.2. List of posters

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17481712>

INSTITUT OGRONICTWA

RESEARCH & INNOVATION

Sebastian Siarkowski¹, Dorota Konopacka¹, Monika Mieszczakowska-Fraj¹,
Alexia Jauniau², Agnès Giboreau², Dawid Wieloch²

¹The National Institute of Horticultural Research,
the HortiFood Processing Centre,

²Institute Lyfe, Sensory and Consumer Research Centre, Lyon, France

LIVING LAB AS SUPPORT FOR THE PROCESSING OF POLISH BERRY FRUITS

Poland is one of the leading producers of berry fruits in Europe, on the other hand market potential of species such as chokeberry (*Aronia melanocarpa*) and haskap (*Lonicera caerulea*) remains underexploited. Despite their exceptional nutritional profiles and well-documented health benefits, their consumption is limited due to low consumer awareness, lack of habitual use, and a distinct, intense sensory character that poses challenges for processors.

As part of the HortiFoodTrends project, a survey among producers and processors helped identify key market and technological barriers. The findings emphasize the need to develop products that meet both consumer expectations and processing capabilities.

To address these challenges, the project applies a modern Living Lab approach – a collaborative innovation model that brings together producers, processors, scientists, and consumers. Using qualitative research (focus groups) conducted in France, the project explored sensory preferences, functional expectations, and product formats most likely to increase acceptance of chokeberry and haskap. These insights form the basis for developing new prototypes with high sensory and market potential.

The aim of the HortiFoodTrends project was to identify the key barriers limiting the market potential of chokeberry and haskap products and to develop innovative product concepts that reflect consumer expectations and processing capabilities.

The project focused on:

Implementation of a collaborative model that brings together producers, processors, scientists, and consumers to jointly design berry-based products with high market, sensory, and technological potential. The adjacent word cloud illustrates key challenges identified by stakeholders, such as bitterness, low consumer awareness, limited availability, and inconvenient product formats – all of which support the need for co-creation in product development.

Identifying sensory preferences – determining which characteristics (e.g., taste, stringency, aroma, texture, appearance) are appreciated or disliked by consumers and how they influence willingness to purchase.

Analyzing consumer perception – assessing the level of awareness, associations with consumption, and psychological or sensory barriers that hinder acceptance of chokeberry and haskap.

Evaluating preferred product formats and functional attributes – exploring which forms (e.g., juice, puree, snack, dairy additive) are most likely to be accepted and which functional features are most desired.

Living Lab

Innovative Collaboration

- Developing berry products
- High sensory & market potential
- Using a participatory approach

The project confirms that a consumer-inclusive approach is essential for turning underutilized berries into accepted, functional, and market-ready products. Living Lab collaboration bridges sensory, technological, and commercial gaps—boosting innovation and uptake.

INTRODUCTION TO LIVING LAB

Haskap berry

INNOVATION DRIVEN BY CONSUMER IDEATION AND VALIDATED IN REAL-MEAL SITUATION: AN APPLICATION TO POLISH BERRIES UNKNOWN IN FRANCE

Chokeberry

The HORTIFOODTRENDS project aims to develop innovative, health-promoting novel foods by applying advanced processing techniques to preserve fruits and vegetables' nutritional and bioactive. It integrates consumer sciences and sensory analysis, aligning with the European Union's "From Farm to Fork" strategy.

The project focuses on berries cultivated in Poland, particularly chokeberries and haskap berries, which are increasingly available but underutilized due to their peculiar astringency and lingering aftertaste. To enhance their appeal and widespread use, the project leverages culinary innovation, sensory evaluation tools, and consumer research conducted in real-consumption situation. In this way, the project wants to create proper communication between the consumer, the fruit producer, the processing sector and science using the Living-Lab approach.

1. Qualitative research aiming to co-create food concepts

During this focus group, the InHort processed ingredients were presented to consumers. The objective was to imagine possible pairing with other ingredients in some recipes, leading to a co-creation of food concepts, including chokeberry and haskap berry.

2. Food concept development by chefs

As a result of the discussion between consumers, 8 initial concepts were developed. Innovation team with Chefs of LIFE Institute are the culinary experts involved in the project: they selected 4 promising food concepts and fine-tuned the recipes, including chokeberry and haskap berry.

<p>Savory – Concept 1</p> <p>Mushrooms velouté, mushrooms in pieces, haskap berry, cream diphon, fresh olive, parmesan crumble topping</p> <p>Dry mushrooms Haskap berry puree</p>	<p>Savory – Concept 2</p> <p>Farfadet of fermented cabbage and caramelized onions with a creamy smoked tofu-chokeberry sauce with chickpeas puree</p> <p>Fermented cabbage Chokeberry puree</p>	<p>Sweet – Concept 3</p> <p>A creamy, lightly caramelized Basque cheesecake with a chokeberry puree-lemon coulis and apple chips topping</p> <p>Chokeberry puree Red apple chips</p>	<p>Sweet – Concept 4</p> <p>A chou pastry with croquette filled with a mousseline cream made from Haskap berry puree, haskap coulis, heart and roundly caramelized hazelnuts</p> <p>Haskap berry puree</p>
---	--	---	---

3. Consumers' feedback on food concept developed

Qualitative research in sensory focus group was run to collect strengths and weaknesses of each recipe; sensory attributes measurement and improvement leads identified.

Selection of the best food concept: "Basque cheesecake made with chokeberry and fresh cheese, served with chokeberry lemon coulis and crispy apple chips".

The main improvement identified was to intensify the chokeberry taste by increasing the berry content from 8% (Product REF) to 20% (Product NEW) in the cheesecake.

4. Quantitative research on the selected food concept

A monadic pure hedonic quantitative test on 2 versions of the cheesecake recipe in real meal situations was run at LIFE Institute restaurant, collecting feedback from 70 consumers over 2 weeks. The objective was to validate the sensory improvements implemented by the chefs on the recipe and check the overall appreciation of the dessert by French consumers.

Results demonstrated that the chokeberry increase in cheesecake didn't impact the overall liking score, despite a slightly too acidic/lack of sweetness sensory profile. Crispy apple chips were really liked.

The process demonstrates the value of combining qualitative phases with consumers and culinary creativity with chefs to link food habits and preferences with new ingredients, providing concrete recipes and usage of berries to be further pursued at the EU level. Living Lab collaboration bridges sensory, technological, and commercial gaps — boosting innovation and uptake.

The project confirms that a consumer-inclusive approach is essential for turning underutilized berries into accepted, functional, and market-ready products to get closer to a commercialization opportunity to be developed for the Polish berries.

Email contact: ajauniau@institutliffe.com; sebastian.siarkowski@inhort.pl

SENSORY LIVING-LAB AS OPPORTUNITY FOR “SUPER” BERRY FRUIT PRODUCT ADOPTION

WHAT DOES „SUPER” BERRY MEANS?

„Super” berry in Poland is recognized to berry fruits outstandingly rich in anthocyanins, like chokeberry, blackcurrant or haskap berry, which could be exploit especially valuable constituents of functional food.

“SUPER” BERRIES, AN UNDERESTIMATED GIFT OF NATURE

All the black 'super' berries" - chokeberry, haskap berry or blackcurrant are characterized with outstanding dietetic properties.

	Vitamin C mg/100 g	Anthocyanins mg/100 g	Dietary Fibers g/100 g
Blackcurrant	160-285	130-400	7,9
Haskapberry	30-180	140-1100	3,0
Chokeberry	20-30	200-1000	5,3

Despite longstanding efforts to popularize preserves based on that 'superfruits', they are still underestimated by consumers. What's more food producers are afraid of processing them. In order to give berries a chance for wider acceptance among modern consumers, the Institute of Horticulture supported by international (Polish, Denmark, French) consortium, is implementing the 'HortiFoodTrends'.

The aim of the project is, among others, to propose berry products that will have both acceptable sensory characteristic and significant health-promoting properties. It is expected to become a tool fostering human well-being and agri-food sector capacity.

RESEARCH APPROACH

One of the important participants of the Living-Lab approach in the presented project are Polish berry producers and potential investors, especially processing plants manager. As part of the project, a survey was conducted in which they were asked about various aspects of the production of 'super' berries, including asking them to indicate barriers to the introduction of these species into the market.

The survey was conducted among participants of an industry conference dedicated to Polish berry producers. Twenty entities participated in the survey. Responses were anonymous and data submission was voluntary.

WHAT WOULD ENCOURAGE YOU TO INCLUDE “SUPER BERRIES” IN YOUR DAILY DIET?

Would you agree to answer a few questions?

CREATING INNOVATION AS A CONCEPT OF COOPERATION BETWEEN FOUR SECTORS

BARRIERS IDENTIFIED IN THE INTRODUCTION OF PROCESSED SUPER BERRY PRODUCTS TO THE MARKET

- (1) very low consumer awareness of chokeberry and haskap berry
- (2) difficulties related to their intense and specific taste
- (3) the lack of well-established buying habits for high anthocyanins

Haskap berries exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, antihypertensive, anticancer, procognitive, cardio-, hepato-, and neuroprotective properties. Recent reports also indicate that consuming haskap berries can increase running performance and speed in recreational runners, likely due to improved vascular endothelial function and the body's ability to cope with exercise-induced oxidative stress.

Chokeberries, particularly black chokeberries (*Aronia melanocarpa*), are known for their rich content of antioxidants and polyphenols, which contribute to a variety of health benefits. These benefits include potential cardioprotective, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and antioxidant effects. They may also help in improving blood pressure, cholesterol levels, and blood sugar regulation